

A NEW ALTERNATIVE IN MIGRAINE TREATMENT: ELETRIPTAN HYDROBROMIDE BUCCAL ORGANOGELS

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ABSTRACT

Migraine is a disorder characterized by severe, intermittent throbbing pain in the head, often accompanied by sensitivity to light and sound, as well as nausea and vomiting. Eletriptan hydrobromide (EHB) is a highly selective serotonin 5-HT_{1B/1D} receptor agonist administered orally in the acute treatment of moderate or severe migraine attacks. In migraine patients, pain-induced vomiting and nausea may complicate medication intake. Inhibition of critical gastrointestinal motility and delayed gastric emptying time during a migraine attack is also a major problem. Taking into consideration all these data, the importance of unconventional dosage forms in migraine treatment emerges. The fact is that buccal formulations are important in terms of rapid effect, easy use in patients with swallowing difficulties, and ease of use in patients with nausea/vomiting complaints, and in cases requiring drug intake without water.

KEYWORDS: Migraine, Buccal, Eletriptan hydrobromide, Organogel

RELEVANCE OF THE TOPIC

With this buccal formulation, it is aimed to offer a new alternative treatment that will make a difference in the current migraine treatment.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

Development and *in vitro* characterization of EHB buccal organogel formulations for migraine treatment.

RESEARCH METHODS

Organogels were prepared by using the seed oil/olive oil. Aerosil and Ethyl cellulose were used as gelling agent. Tocopheryl acetate chosen as an antioxidant. The formulations were evaluated for their pH values, textural, rheological and mucoadhesive properties. At the same time *in vitro* release studies were carried out.

MAIN RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

Figure 1 The flow and viscosity curve of the formulations at 25 °C and 37 °C

Figure 2 The oscillation curve of the formulations at 25°C and 37°C

The pH values and mechanical properties of the gel formulations were observed suitable for buccal application. Mucoadhesion of O-1-M-2 and O-2-M were found $91,53 \pm 5,174$ and $158,50 \pm 8,746$ respectively.

As a result of our project work, it has been shown that organogel formulations containing EHB are potential formulations that can be used buccally in the treatment of migraine and have the appropriate properties.

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